

Journal home page:
<http://www.iajpr.com/index.php/en/>

**INDO AMERICAN
 JOURNAL OF
 PHARMACEUTICAL
 RESEARCH**

Proteomics Tools for Oral Cancer Biomarker Discovery

Nishant Sharma^{1,2}, Dr .B.R Srivastav¹ and Dr. Archana Shrivatav²*

¹ Cancer Hospital and Research Institute Gwalior India

² College of Life Sciences Gwalior India

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 26 August
2012

Available online 9
Sep 2012

Keywords

Proteomics,
Proteomic tool, Oral
cancer.

ABSTRACT

Proteomic study of human body fluid (saliva and serum) holds assure as a non-invasive method to identify biomarkers for human oral cancer. The evolving of novel technologies allows researchers to aid the inclusive analyses of proteomes in cancer. The protein expression pattern of tumors cells measure by proteomics technologies that provide opportunities to discover potentially new biomarkers for the early detection and diagnosis of oral cancer. Different proteomic tools such as 2DPAGE, 2D-DIGE, MALDI, SELDI-TOF-MS LC-MS/MS technology, protein arrays, iTRAQ, ICAT and MudPIT have been used for discrepancy analysis of various biological samples, including cell lysates, Saliva, serum, plasma and tumors tissue to better understand the molecular foundation of cancer pathogenesis and the validation and characterization of disease-associated proteins. This review covers a selection of advances in the dominion of proteomics and its promise for oral cancer biomarker discovery. It also introduces sample preparation and discusses current challenges that need to be defeat and the efforts of the Early Detection of oral cancer and promoting biomarker discovery for conversion at the clinical level.

Corresponding author

Nishant Sharma, Cancer Hospital and Research Institute Gwalior India

E-Mail: nishant7373@yahoo.co.in

Please cite this article in press as Nishant Sharma, Proteomics Tools for Oral Cancer Biomarker Discovery. Indo American Journal of Pharm Research. 2012:2(9).

Introduction

Cancer scraps a major public health challenge even with progress in detection and therapy. A large portion of the US population will develop cancer during their lifetime.¹ with ~500 000 individuals dying annually from the disease². Oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) is the sixth most common cancer worldwide. Despite the tremendous improvements in surgery, radiotherapy and chemotherapy, the prognosis for patients with OSCC is more or less unchanged for the past 3 decades. This is because oral cancers are often diagnosed at late stage when the disease has metastasized from the primary tumor site.³⁻⁵

Proteins play a central role in cell function and cell structure. Some proteins are down-regulated and others are up-regulated with the onset of disease, depending on a protein's specific function, undergoing disease-specific posttranslational modifications.⁶⁻⁷ This identification of changes in protein profile that occur during pathological condition could lead to the discovery of protein biomarkers and novel strategies for the improvement of detection and diagnosis of oral cancer without any unfairness. Various steps of gene expressions are used for biomarker Discovery (**Fig-1**).

Human fluid such as saliva, plasma, tissue fluid contains proteins that can be informative for disease detection and surveillance of oral health. Comprehensive analysis and identification of the proteomic content in human fluid is a necessary first step for discovery of protein markers. The article will review the recent advances in human proteome analysis. We aim to summarize the proteomics technologies currently used for global analysis of proteins and to elaborate on the application of proteomics to discovery of disease biomarkers, in particular for oral cancer and discuss some of the critical challenges and perspectives for this promising field.

The impact of human saliva proteome analysis in the search for clinically relevant disease biomarkers will be realized through advances made using proteomics technologies among the important tools critical to detection, diagnosis, treatment, monitoring, and prognosis are biomarkers.⁸ the protein composition of whole saliva also Change during radiotherapy in patients with oral or pharyngeal cancer.⁹

Serum content Proteins such as albumin, transferrin, haptoglobin, immunoglobulins, and lipoproteins.¹⁰ Low molecular weight human serum proteins, peptides, and other small components have been associated with pathological conditions such as cancer.¹¹ Serum proteins may often serve as indicators of disease and is a rich source for biomarker discovery.¹²

Biomarkers are measurable and quantifiable biological parameters that can serve as indices for health-related assessments, such as disease diagnosis, environmental exposure and its effects, metabolic processes and epidemiological studies.¹³

Diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers are quantifiable traits that help clinical oncologists at the first interaction with the suspected patients. These particularly aid in (i) identifying who is at risk, (ii) diagnose at an early stage, (iii) select the best treatment modality, and (iv) monitor response to treatment.¹⁴

Proteomics is a dominant approach for global study of the structure and function of all proteins expressed in a biological system. Mapping proteomes, the protein complements to genomes, from tissues, cells and organisms is being used to identify new protein targets, to explore mechanisms of action or toxicology of pharmaceuticals, and to discover new disease biomarkers for clinical and diagnostic applications. (**Fig-2**) Novel technologies that are designed to progress the molecular analyses of healthy and diseased human cells are poised to develop the field of health and disease. Advances in the fields of genomics and proteomics that provide insights into the molecular complexity of the disease process and thus enable the development of tools to help in treatment as well as in detection and prevention.

Proteomic Tools

Proteome is the complete complement of proteins that can be expressed by a given genome or cell and study of proteome is called Proteomics that aims at global profiling and the characterization of proteins, it is a powerful approach to discover protein biomarkers in human diseases and cancer for clinical and diagnostic applications.¹⁵

Figure-1 The Progression of Carcinogenesis, screening opportunities of identifying biomarkers.

The recent developments several proteomics technologies including two dimensional polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (2D PAGE), surface enhanced laser desorption/ionisation time of flight (SELDI-TOF), protein arrays, isotope coded affinity tags (ICAT), iTRAQ and multidimensional protein identification technology (MudPIT) are the approaches creature implemented in cancer research. 2D-PAGE and SELDI-TOF are the main technologies used in saliva and serum of oral cancer research however other technologies such as protein arrays, ICAT, iTRAQ and MudPIT also offer great potential for future biomarker discovery of oral cancer. Due to particular sensitivity and highly accurate mass measurements, mass spectrometry (MS) has become one of the core technologies for proteomics. A very common proteomics way is to map out proteins using 2-D gel electrophoresis (2-DE) followed by in-gel digestion and MS measurement of the resulting peptide fragments, either by mass fingerprinting or tandem MS (MS/MS), to identify proteins from each gel spot. Such global analysis can also be performed by using a "shotgun" proteomics approach, in which 2-D liquid chromatography (LC) and tandem MS are typically used to analyze a fully digested proteomic sample. Both approaches rely on searching protein or DNA sequence databases to identify the proteins.

A variety of MS techniques, including surface-enhanced laser desorption/ionization (SELDI), matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization (MALDI), MALDI-TOF/TOF and LC-MS/MS have been extensively applied to biomarker study in human oral cancers. SELDI provides rapid profiling of peptides and small proteins and has been applied to biomarker studies in oral cancer.¹⁶⁻¹⁹ a variety of stable isotope reagents have been developed for relative quantification in proteomics, including ICAT (isotope-coded affinity tagging), SILAC (Stable isotope labeling with amino acids in cell culture), AQUA (absolute quantification using internal standard peptides), iTRAQ (isotope tagging for relative and absolute quantitation), etc. Most methods enable quantification in the full MS scan, and peptide identification based on subsequent fragmentation (MS/MS) of

precursor ions, with the exception of iTRAQ, where both the identification and quantification are performed in the MS/MS scan.²⁰

Isotope-Coded Affinity Tags

Isotope-coded affinity tags (ICAT) use stable isotope labeling that facilitates direct qualitative and quantitative comparisons of paired protein samples or mixtures. They contain a protein-reactive group, an ethylene glycol linker and a biotin tag. This method, analogous to the microarray approach for assessing differential gene expression between two cell states, uses a chemical group or label made in two different isotopic forms: heavy and light. The heavy isotope is added to one sample (e.g., cancer cells), whereas the lighter isotope is added to the second sample (healthy cells).²¹ Two different isotope tags are generated by using linkers that contain either eight hydrogen atoms (d0, light reagent) or eight deuterium atoms (d8, heavy reagent) which bind covalently to cysteine moieties of amino acid within protein(s). Both samples are mixed, digested with trypsin, fractionated by avidin affinity chromatography and then these differentially tagged peptides are scanned in a mass spectrometer. The mass spectrometer measures the relative abundance of heavy and light peptide forms in each sample and identifies each peptide by generating and analyzing the peptide fingerprints. That provides global view of protein abundance in cells or tissues in two different states. This is particularly important to biomarker discovery because expression analysis of all proteins and identification of the changes that are a function of a disease process give us molecular handles to target intervention strategies. One disadvantage of ICAT is that only cysteine containing peptides can be labelled. Approximately 10% of proteins do not have cysteine, therefore they will not be detected by ICAT.

Isobaric tag for relative and absolute quantitation

A similar isobaric labeling technology to ICAT, called iTRAQ, that labels amine residues in peptides has been recently developed.²⁰ iTRAQ contains a set of four isobaric reagents and therefore can analyze up to four protein samples at one time. After trypsin digestion, samples are labeled with four independent iTRAQ reagents. The reporter groups of the iTRAQ reagents will split from the peptide and generate small fragments for each sample with mass/charges (m/z) of 114, 115, 116, and 117. The intensity of each of these peaks represents the quantity of small reporter group fragments and thus represents the quantity of a peptide sample. Peaks in the spectrum graph are used to identify peptide sequences and therefore protein sequences. By comparing the amounts of peptides labelled with each iTRAQ reagent, quantitative differences can be readily measured. A comparative analysis of iTRAQ and ICAT suggests that the information generated by the two methods is complementary. Both methods have some advantages and disadvantages over the other. Unlike iTRAQ, ICAT is preferred for low abundant proteins including signalling molecules, however overlapping peaks in the MS spectrum can compromise the quality of results. On the other hand, apart from nonspecific nature of labelling, iTRAQ requires lengthy sample processing separately that increases the chances of experimental variation.²²

Multidimensional protein identification technology

MudPIT is a non-gel approach that uses multidimensional high-pressure liquid chromatography (LC/LC) separation, tandem mass spectrometry and database searching.²³ MudPIT allow a rapid and simultaneous separation and identification of proteins and peptides in a complex mixture without the need for pre- or post-separation labelling, which is not possible in 2D electrophoresis, ICAT or iTRAQ.²⁴ The complex protein mixture is digested with a specific protease, then peptide fragments are allowed to separate in parallel with two dimensional liquid chromatography using a strong cation exchange (SCX) column that separate peptides based on charge, and then by a reverse phase (RP) column based on hydrophobicity. Eluted peptides are identified by tandem mass spectrometry and the technique is extremely sensitive and reproducible. One of the major disadvantages of MudPIT is in identifying quantitative differences in protein expression across protein mixtures.²⁵ In a comparative study with 2D-electrophoresis, MudPIT has been reported to demonstrate superior detection efficiency.²⁴

Figure- 2 Overview of Proteomics**MALDI**

Matrix-assisted desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS) allows the analysis and identification of very small amounts of protein isolated from the gel.^{21,26-29} MALDI can be applied as a tool of monitoring of the composition changes in the saliva without requirement for extensive pretreatment all thought. The MALDI fingerprinting analysis only provide information regarding molecular weight combination of MALDI with SDS PAGE and within gel enzymatic digestion can provide more detail information to careeries protein in this preliminary investigation unusually higher concentration of α amylase and albumine appired in saliva of patient with oral cancer further investigation is required to validates a possible diagnostic tool .³⁰

MALDI TOF/TOF-based platform offers several advantages including high throughput, mass range and accuracy, selective MS/MS analysis based on MS information, and an easy to interpret data structure.³¹ Peptide identification can be performed on the same MALDI plate afterwards by MS/MS. The ability to re-examine and verify the same sample set can be very beneficial for quantitative applications. MS with isotope coded tagging has the potential for high sensitivity, coverage and throughput.³² In This gel-free proteomic strategy also holds significant promise for the rapid identification of protein markers/targets for human diseases.^{33, 34}

The procedure involves the precipitation of the sample molecules with an excess of matrix material, such as α -cyano-4-hydroxycinnamic acid or dihydroxybenzoic acid.³⁵ The precipitated solid is then irradiated with laser pulses and the matrix material imparts energy to the biomolecules. The matrix materials have absorbances at the wavelength of the laser, and the molecules are subjected to a process of desorption and ionization accompanied by fragmentation. The mass spectrometer then measures the mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) of the protein, peptide, or peptide fragments. Mass separation can be achieved based on the TOF, generation of quadrupole electric fields, or ejection of ions from an ion trap. MALDI can be linked to any one of the above three methods.

The disadvantage of this method lies in the low sensitivity for detection of low-abundance proteins in a two-dimensional spot. The specified spot may contain multiple components, and the signals generated, through peptide digests, by ions of low abundance are lost in this approach.³⁶

LC-MS/MS

LC-MS/MS and nanospray MS/MS data were processed to search the Swissprot protein database using the MASCOT search engine (Matrix Science, London, UK). LC fractionation with MALDI-MS and tandem MS is practical used to identifying oral fluid biomarkers is simpler than other body fluids such as serum. The ability to sequence information for a specific peptide in the presence of multiple peptides in the sample. Reversed-phase LC is used to concentrate and separate peptides from extremely complex mixtures before sequencing by MS.²⁹ LC-MS/MS has been demonstrated to enhance separation and identification of analytes in the low femtomolar range.²¹ Dibenzo[a,l] pyrene (DB[a, l]P) is the most potent carcinogenic polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon found in tobacco smoke, (LC-MS/MS) method to detect and quantify DB[a, l]P in oral tissues.³⁷

A single LC-MS/MS analysis thus offers the possibility of isolating and sequencing hundreds of selected peptides from one sample. An additional advantage of this technique is the ability to identify protein targets of reactive electrophiles and map the adducts to the specific amino acid.³⁸ This approach could be used for novel biomarker discovery and help researchers to realize the mechanisms through which environmental exposures may initiate carcinogenesis through protein modifications.

Surface-enhanced Laser Desorption/Ionization

The development of surface enhanced laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (SELDI-TOF MS), a high throughput and extremely sensitive proteomic approach that allows protein expression profiling of large sample sets.^{39,40}

This technique allows proteins/peptides to be profiled from different biological samples on a variety of chemically (*e.g.* anionic, cationic, hydrophobic, hydrophilic, metal affinity capture) or biochemically (*e.g.* immobilized antibody, receptor, DNA, enzyme) defined chromatographic Surfaces. A small amount of sample is loaded onto Protein Chip arrays that selectively bind different subsets of proteins in crude samples by adsorption, partition, electrostatic interaction or affinity chromatography according to their surface chemistries. After incubation period for some time, unbound proteins and unspecific substances are washed away with an appropriate buffer and water. The TOF reader records the time-of-flight and calculates the accurate molecular weight of proteins/peptides in the form of a spectral map containing mass to charge ratios (m/z) and intensities corresponding to each bound protein/peptide. Biomarker Wizard software analyses the spectral map and detects differentially expressed protein/peptides with statistical significance. An increase in published research using SELDI-ToF in the past few years itself has demonstrated its potential for the early detection of cancer, especially for low molecular weight cancer-associated proteins.

SELDI has several advantages over other existing technologies, such as LC-MS, two-dimensional gel electrophoresis-coupled MS and fluorescent-based binding assays, for high-throughput screening because of its versatility, ease of use, speed, and low cost. It is rapid, reproducible, highly sensitive (detection limit in the femtomolar range), and readily adaptable to a diagnostic format.⁴¹ Additionally, molecules that have been traditionally difficult to identify have been detected with ease by use of the SELDI platform.⁴²

The SELDI-TOF MS technique to generate multiple proteomic spectra from plasma samples of patients with HNSCC and those without known neoplastic disease and used bioinformatics method "Lasso" algorithm

developed by Tibshirani.⁴³ They observed extrapolate proteomic patterns that can best discriminate HNSCC patients from noncancer controls. This approach can be used to separate HNSCC patients from noncancer controls with moderate sensitivity and specificity. Previous study found that this technique can be used to detect HNSCC with moderate sensitivity of 68% and a specificity of 73%.⁴⁴

Protein arrays

Protein arrays are being used for drug discovery, biomarker identification and molecular profiling of cellular material.⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸ Protein arrays are generated by spotting antibodies⁴⁵ or other affinity reagents, such as aptamers, purified proteins,⁴⁹ peptides⁴⁷ or fractionated proteins⁴⁶, onto some sort of matrix either on flat solid phases or in capillary systems to generate protein arrays. The sample is applied to the array to allow specific binding of the sample to the array and then the arrays are washed to remove the unbound fraction. The process can also be reversed whereby the protein samples of interest are spotted onto the matrix and then probed with different affinity reagents. The wider application of protein arrays in biomedical research is still limited, partly because of the cost of producing antibodies and the limited availability of antibodies with high specificity and high affinity for the target. Additionally, the difficulties associated with preserving proteins in their biologically active conformation before analysis with protein arrays further limits the application of this technology as a routine proteomic strategy.

Sample preparation

The most fundamental steps for oral cancer proteomics are sample preparation. This is important because it may affect reproducibility as a result of the heterogeneity of proteins derived from cell populations.⁵⁰ From the time of sample collection to the point when proteins are introduced for analysis, multiple factors come into play. Efforts should be made to process all the samples in as similar a manner as possible. Cancer cells should be rendered free of stroma and necrotic tissue and contaminating serum proteins and blood cells to ensure that findings directly relate to the tumor in question.⁵¹ Mechanical methods such as surface scraping and fine-needle aspiration have been successfully used for capturing cancer cells and blood.⁵² Calcium starvation and other nonenzymatic methods, such as immunomagnetic separation, have also been used to isolate pure populations of cancer cells.^{53, 54} For saliva sample Unstimulated whole saliva collect from the patients individuals after rinsed their mouths several times with deionized water, the accumulated saliva in the floor of the mouth under the tongue collect in sterile disposable sample collector.⁵⁵ All sample Should be stored frozen at (-20°C) in polyethylene tubes.

Bioinformatics

Bioinformatics tools are connected works of proteomic analyses because the development of proteomic technologies incorporating high-throughput methods relies on powerful data analysis tools. Bioinformatic tools are necessary for multiple components of proteomic investigations, including analysis, storage, management, search, and retrieval. Bioinformatic tools are being developed around current proteomic platforms of two-dimensional gel electrophoresis, MS, and arrays. Tools developed to analyze two-dimensional electrophoresis protein patterns incorporate software applications possessing user-friendly interfaces for linearization and merging of scanned images, segmentation and detection of protein spots on the images, matching, and editing.⁵⁶ Commercial two-dimensional image analysis software available to the proteomics community include ImageMasterTM (Amersham Biosciences), Melanie 3 (GeneBio), ProgenesisTM (Nonlinear Dynamics), PDQuestTM 2-D Analysis Software (Bio-Rad Laboratories), ProteinMineTM (Scimagix), and the Z3 2D-Gel Analysis System (Compugen Limited).⁵⁷

Software tools such as RADARS (Rapid Automated Data Archiving and Retrieval Software) are beginning to address this issue.⁵⁸ The RADARS system automatically initiates database searches for protein identification from raw data files in addition to storing the processed data and search results in a relational database.⁵⁸ Current methods of analysis of MS data include peptide mass fingerprinting or peptide mass analysis.⁵⁹⁻⁶¹, peptide sequence tag query⁶⁰⁻⁶², and MS/MS-ion search analysis.^{60, 63}

Challenges

In distinction to the genome, the proteome is forceful and is in constant flux because of a combination of factors. These include differential splicing of the respective mRNAs, posttranslational modifications, and temporal and functional regulation of gene expression. The inclusive study of proteins has many exceptional difficulties that set it apart from comprehensive studies of genes and transcripts. One difficulty is that tertiary structure of the proteins. Any test, based on protein binding depends on maintaining the native conformation of the protein. Another difficulty is that low-abundance proteins in biological systems. For this difficulty an amplification method to be developed for protein studies. Proteins regulation also show synthesis degradation and reversible modifications such as phosphorylation and glycosylation. In addition, RNA splicing can produce splice variants that are highly homologous but differ in function. The proteomics revolt confidently will advance to overcome many of these hurdles and provide us with information for biomarkers discovery and the prevention of cancer.

Perspective

Human body fluid Saliva and serum of oral cancer patients contains signature peptides and proteins that potentially useful for oral cancer detection and diagnosis. Approximately 27% of the whole-saliva proteins are found in plasma.⁶⁴ Now that the outline of the human genome has been completed, the field of proteomics has a vast protein networks that both control and are controlled by the information encoded by the genome.⁶⁵ So various proteomics technology helps in proteomics research and biomarker discovery in the field of oral cancer. Through careful analysis of these systems, a detailed understanding of the molecular causes and consequences of oral cancer could come out.

References

1. Chaurand .P, DaGue B.B, Pearsall. R.S, Threadgill D.W, Caprioli R.M ,Profiling proteins from azoxymethane-induced colon tumors at the molecular level by matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization mass spectrometry, *Proteomics* 2001,1320-1326.
2. American Cancer Society, *Cancer facts and figures* 1996 ,American Cancer Society Atlanta.
3. Brinkman, B.M, Wong, D.T,Disease mechanism and biomarkers of oral squamous cell carcinoma,*Curr. Opin. Oncol* 2006),18, 228.
4. Hu. S,Wong, D.T, Oral cancer proteomics,*Curr. Opin. Mol. Ther* 2007,9, 467.
5. Ye, H, Wang. A, Lee, B.Yu, T. Shen, S.; Peng, T, Hu, S,Crowe, D,Zhou, X, Proteomic based identification of manganese superoxide dismutase 2 (SOD2) as a metastasis marker for oral squamous cell carcinoma, *Cancer Genomics Proteomics* 2008,5, 85.
6. Masters .CL, Beyreuther. K, Alzheimer's disease,BMJ 1998,316: 446-448.
7. Bechtel .PE., Hickey. RJ., Schnaper. L., Sekowski .JW, Long. BJ, Freund. R,A unique form of proliferating cell nuclear antigen is present in malignant breast cells, *Cancer Res* 1998, 58: 3264-3269.
8. Stryer. L, W.H ,Freeman The bio chemical activity of α amylase change during oral cancer *Biochemistry Newyork* 1981,376.
9. Pitiyage. G, Tilakaratne. WM, Tavassoli .M, Warnakulasuriya .S ,Molecular markers in oral epithelial dysplasia,Review, *J Oral Pathol Med* 2009,38:737-52.
10. Turner, M. W and Hulme, B.The Plasma Proteins: An Introduction1970 ,Pitman Medical & Scientific Publishing Co., Ltd., London.
11. Petricoin, E. F, Ardekani, A. M , Hitt, B. A, Levine, P. J, Fusaro, V. A, Steinberg, S. M, Mills, G. B, Simone, C, Fishman, D. A, Kohn, E. C, and Liotta, L. A,Use of proteomic patterns in serum to identify ovarian ,cancer. *Lancet* 359 2002, 572– 577.
12. Björhall .K, Miliotis. T, Davidsson. P,Comparison of different depletion strategies for improved resolution in proteomic analysis of human serum samples2005,5(1):307-17.

13. Srinivas. P.R, Kramer. B.S, Srivastava .S, Trends in biomarker research for cancer detection. ,*Lancet Oncol* 2 2001, 698-704.
14. Ludwig. J.A, John N. Weinstein, biomarkers in cancer staging prognosis and treatment selection, *Nat Rev Cancer* 5 2005, 845-56.
15. M. R. Wilkins, J.C. Sanchez, A. A. Gooley, "Progress with proteome projects: why all proteins expressed by a genome should be identified and how to do it," *Biotechnology and Genetic Engineering Reviews*, vol. 13 1995, pp. 19–50.
16. Petricoin. E.F, Ornstein. D.K, Paweletz. C.P, Ardekani. A, Hackett .P.S, Hitt .B.A, Velasco .A, Trucco. C, Wiegand. L, Wood .K, Simone .C.B, Levine .P.J, Linehan. W.M, Emmert, Buck .M.R, Steinberg .S.M, Kohn. E.C and Liotta .L.A, Serum proteomic patterns for detection of prostate cancer,*J Natl Cancer Inst* 94 2002, 1576-1578.
17. Jacobs .I.J and Menon. U, Progress and challenges in screening for early detection of ovarian cancer, *Mol Cell Proteomics* 3 2004, 355-366.
18. Adam .B.L, Qu .Y, Davis .J.W, Ward .M.D, Clements .M.A, Cazares .L.H, Semmes O.J, Schellhammer P.F, Yasui Y, Feng Z and Wright G.L Jr, Serum protein fingerprinting coupled with a pattern-matching algorithm distinguishes prostate cancer from benign prostate hyperplasia and healthy men,*Cancer Res* 62 2002,3609-3614.
19. Li .J, Zhang .Z, Rosenzweig .J, Wang Y.Y and Chan D.W: Proteomics and bioinformatics approaches for identification of serum biomarkers to detect breast cancer, *Clin Chem* 48 2002,1296-1304,
20. Ross P.L, Huang, Y.N, Marchese J.N, Williamson .B,Parker K, Hattan S, Khainovski, N,Pillai S,Dey S, Daniels S, Pur kayastha. S, Juhasz, P, Martin S, Bartlet Jones M, He, F,Jacobson, A, Pappin, D.J, *Mol. Cell Proteomics* 3 2004, 1154.
21. Gygi .S.P, Rist .B, Gerber S.A, Turecek .F, Gelb .M.H and Aebersold. R,Quantitative analysis of complex protein mixtures using isotope-coded affinity tags,*Nat Biotechnol* 17(10) 1999,994-999.
22. DeSouza .L, Diehl. G, Rodrigues. M.J, Guo J, Romaschin A.D, Colgan T.J and Siu K.W, Search for cancer markers from endometrial tissues using differentially labeled tags iTRAQ and cICAT with multidimensional liquid chromatography and tandem mass spectrometry, *J Proteome Res* 4(2) 2005,377-386.
23. McDonald W.H and Yates J.R 3rd: Shotgun proteomics and biomarker discovery, *Dis Markers* 18(2) (2002,99-105.
24. Koller. A, Washburn M.P, Lange B.M, Andon N.L, Deciu C, Haynes P.A, Hays L, Schieltz D, Ulaszek R, Wei J, Wolters D and Yates JR 3rd: Proteomic survey of metabolic pathways in rice. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 99(18) 2002, 11969-11974.
25. Washburn MP, Ulaszek R.R and Yates JR 3rd: Reproducibility of quantitative proteomic analyses of complex biological mixtures by multidimensional protein identification technology,*Anal Chem* 75(19) 2003,5054-5061.
26. Chait B.T, Kent S.B, Weighing naked proteins: practical, high-accuracy mass measurement of peptides and proteins, *Science* 1992,257.
27. Dongre A.R, Eng J.K, Yates J.R. Emerging tandem-mass-spectrometry techniques for the rapid identification of proteins ,*Trends Biotechnol* 1997,15:418-425.
28. Neubauer G, King A, Rappsilber J, Calvio C, Watson M, Ajuh P, et al. Mass spectrometry and EST-database searching allows characterization of the multi-protein spliceosome complex,*Nat Genet* 1998,2046-50.
29. Yates J, 3rd. Mass spectrometry and the age of the proteome. *J Mass Spectrom* 1998,33:1-19.

30. Yu-Chie .Chen, Tzu-Ying .Li and Ming-Fei Tsai, analysis of saliva from patients with oral cancer by matrix assisted laser desorption/ionization time of flight mass spectrometry *Rapid commun* 2002, 16:364-369.
31. Pan .S, Zhang .H, Rush .J, Eng .J, Zhang N, Patterson .D, Comb M.J and Aebersold R High throughput proteome screening for biomarker detection. *Mol Cell Proteomics*, 2005, 4: 182-190.
32. Tao W.A and Aebersold .R, Advances in quantitative proteomics via stable isotope tagging and mass spectrometry ,*Curr Opin Biotechnol* 14 2003, 110-118.
33. Moseley M.A, Current trends in differential expression proteomics: isotopically coded tags. *Trends Biotechnol* 2001,9: S10- S16.
34. Martin D.B, Gifford D.R, Wright M.E, Keller A, Yi E, Goodlett D.R, Aebersold R and Nelson P.S ,Quantitative proteomic analysis of proteins released by neoplastic prostate epithelium,*Cancer Res* 64 2004,347-355.
35. Mann M, Hendrickson R.C, Pandey A, Analysis of proteins and proteomes by mass spectrometry, *Annu Rev Biochem* 2001,**70**:437-473.
36. Hancock W.S, Wu S.L, Sheih P, The challenge of developing a sound proteomics strategy, *Proteomics* 2 2002,352-359.
37. Shang-Min Zhang, Kun-Ming Chen, Cesar Aliaga, Krishnegowda Gowdahalli, Shantu Amin, and Karam El-Bayoumy ,Detection of deoxyguanosine adducts in the oral tissues of mice treated with the environmental carcinogen dibenzo[a, l]pyrene by LC-MS/MS, ,*Cancer Research* 2012,1158/1538-7445.
38. Liebler D.C,Proteomic approaches to characterize protein modifications: new tools to study the effects of environmental exposures, *Environ Health Perspect* 2002,**110**:3-9.
39. Hutchens T.W, Yip T.T, New desorption strategies for the massspectrometric analysis of macromolecules, *Rapid Commun Mass Spectrom* 1993,7:576–80.
40. Merchant .M, Weinberger S.R, Recent advancements in surface-enhanced laser desorption/ionization-time of flight-mass spectrometry, *Electrophoresis* 2000,21:1164–77.
41. Feras E.R, Stephens D.J, Walters C.E, Davies H, Austen B.M. The role of cholesterol in the biosynthesis of β -amyloid, *Neuroreport* 1999,**10**:1699-1705.
42. Yip T.T, Van de Water J, Gerswin M.E, Coppel R.L, Hutchens T.W, Cryptic antigenic determinants on the extracellular pyruvate dehydrogenase complex/mimeotope found in primary biliary cirrhosis, *J Biol Chem* **271** 1996, 32825-32833.
43. Tibshirani R, The lasso method for variable selection in the Cox model, *Stat Med* 1997, 16:385–95.
44. Scott .G. Soltys, Quynh Thu. Le, Gongyi Shi, Squamous Cell Cancers,Proteomic Patterns for Detection of Head and NeckDesorption/Ionization Time-of-Flight Mass SpectrometryThe Use of Plasma Surface-Enhanced Laser, *Clin Cancer Res* **10** 2004, 4806-4812.
45. Mendoza L.G, McQuary .P, Mongan .A, Gangadharan .R, Brignac .S and Eggers M,High-throughput microarray-based enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA),*Biotechniques* 27(4) 1999 778-788.
46. Madoz-Gurpide .J, Wang .H, Misek D.E, Brichory .F and Hanash SM,Protein based microarrays: a tool for probing the proteome of cancer cells and tissues ,*Proteomics* 1(10) 2001, 1279-1287.
47. Houseman B.T, Huh J.H, Kron S.J and Mrksich M,Peptide chips for the quantitative evaluation of protein kinase activity,*Nat Biotechnol* 20(3) 2002,270-274.
48. Woodbury R.L, Varnum S.M and Zangar R.C, Elevated HGF levels in sera from breast cancer patients detected using a protein microarray ELISA, *J Proteome Res* 1(3) 2002,233-237.

49. Ge H, UPA, a universal protein array system for quantitative detection of protein-protein, protein-DNA, protein-RNA and protein-ligand interactions. *Nucleic Acids Res* 28(2) 2000. e3.
50. Herbert B, Advances in protein solubilization for two-dimensional electrophoresis., *Electrophoresis* 201999, 660-663.
51. Simpson R.J, Dorow D.S, Cancer proteomics: from signaling networks to tumor markers, *Trends Biotechnol* 19 2001, S40-S48.
52. Franzen B, Hirano T, Okuzawa K, Uryu K, Alaiya AA, Linder S, Auer G, Sample preparation of human tumors prior to two-dimensional electrophoresis of proteins, *Electrophoresis* 16 1995, 1087-1089.
53. Page M.J, Amess B, Townsend R.R, Parekh R, Herath A, Brusten L, Proteomic definition of normal human luminal and myoepithelial breast cells purified from reduction mammoplasties, *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 96 1999, 12589-12594.
54. Reymond M.A, Sanchez J.C, Schneider C, Rohwer P, Tortola S, Hohenberger W, Specific sample preparation in colorectal cancer, *Electrophoresis* 18 1997, 622-624.
55. Nishanian, P, Aziz N, Chung J, Detelsr R and Fahey J.L, Oral Fluids as an alternative to serum for measurement of markers of immune activation, *Clin. Diagn. Lab. Immunol* 5 1998, 507-512.
56. Monardo P.J, Boutell T, Garrels J.I, Latter G.I, A distributed system for two-dimensional gel analyses, *Comput Appl Biosci* 10 1994, 137-143.
57. Chakravarti D.N, Fiske M.J, Fletcher L.D, Zagursky R.J, Mining genomes and mapping proteomes: identification and characterization of protein subunit vaccines, *Dev Biol* 103 2000, 81-90.
58. Field H.I, Fenyo D, Beavis R.C, RADARS, a bioinformatics solution that automates proteome mass spectral analysis, optimizes protein identification, and archives data in a relational database, *Proteomics* 2 2002, 36-47.
59. Zhang W, Chait B.T. ProFound: an expert system for protein identification using mass spectrometric peptide mapping information, *Anal Chem* 72 2000, 2482-2489.
60. Perkins D.N, Pappin D.J, Creasy D.M, Cottrell J.S, Probability-based protein identification by searching sequence databases using mass spectrometry data, *Electrophoresis* 20 1999, 3551-3567.
61. Clauser K.R, Baker P, Burlingame A.L, Role of accurate mass measurement (± 10 ppm) in protein identification strategies employing MS or MS/MS and database searching, *Anal Chem* 71 1999, 2871-2882.
62. Fenyo D, Qin J, Chait B.T. Protein identification using mass spectrometric information, *Electrophoresis* 19 1998, 998-1005.
63. Eng J.K, McCormack A.L, Yates J.R, An approach to correlate tandem mass spectral data of proteins with amino acid sequences in a protein database, *J Am Soc Mass Spectrom* 5 1994, 976-989.
64. Loo J.A, Yan W, Ramachandran .P, Wong D.T, Comparative Human Salivary and Plasma Proteomes 2010.
65. Herrmann P.C, Liotta L.A, Petricoin E.F, III. Cancer proteomics: the state of the art, *Dis Markers* 17 2001, 49-57.

